

Role of surfactants and solvent parameters in the mechanical and barrier performance of chlorobutyl rubber nanocomposites

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Abstract : A special class of butyl rubber, namely chlorobutyl rubber which exhibits superior air impermeability is the elastomer of choice for the inner tubes and liners of tires. Different varieties of layered silicates were mixed with chlorobutyl rubber and nanocomposites were prepared using solvents with varying cohesive energy density and the effect of solvent-clay and solvent-rubber parameters in determining the properties of the nanocomposites were studied. Different characterization techniques like XRD and TEM were used to characterize the aforementioned composites. The different organo clay moieties (cloisite 10A, 15A) utilized in this work were chosen to investigate the effects of the amine surfactant structure on the dispersion of clay particles in chlorobutyl rubber matrix. The uniform dispersions of nanoclay obtained in the chlorobutyl rubber matrix will definitely enable the material to exhibit better working time or breakthrough times and would make the material suitable for chemical protective clothing. Moreover the intercalated and exfoliated geometry of the nanocomposites is a sure indication of excellent mechanical properties of these materials which pave way for the utilization of these materials in automotive, industrial and aerospace applications.

Keywords : Chlorobutyl rubber, layered silicates, chemical protective clothing, working time.

Introduction

In recent times, nanocomposites consisting of clays and polymers have been found to have improved properties including mechanical properties, barrier properties and enhanced thermal stability. Structure and properties of these nanocomposites are mostly governed by the compatibility of polymer matrix with the organically modified layered silicates having 1 nm thickness of silicate platelets. Montmorillonite clays like cloisite 10A and 15A belong to the (2 : 1) phyllosilicate family where positively charged sodium ions are sandwiched between the negative silicate layers. Organic cations (organo ammonium or organo phosphonium) are incorporated in the interlayer by substitution of Na⁺ ions to make the inorganic materials more compatible with the organic polymer matrix. The polymer chains occupy positions in between the silicate layers giving rise to intercalated or exfoliated nanocomposites. In some cases the quasi-regular distribution of silicate layers will lead to the formation of incompletely intercalated nanocomposites where both the exfoliated and intercalated configuration co-ex-

ists¹⁻⁶. The improved properties are associated to the level of dispersal and exfoliation of the organoclay platelets in the polymer matrix.

Literature suggests that by preparing the nanocomposites through solution mixing brings about better exfoliation/delamination and dispersion of nanoparticles in a polymer matrix^{7,8}. In the case of solution mixing, solvent plays a very significant role in shaping the properties of nanocomposites. It is likely that the solvents may be either the same or different. Complete dispersion of clay particle in a polymer is indeed a challenging situation. Till date many reports are on hand on the preparation of nanocomposites by solution mixing⁷⁻¹². But none of these papers have dealt on the correlation between mechanical properties of vulcanized rubber nanocomposites and nature of solvents used for solution mixing. Ho and Glinka¹³ have given a description of the effect of solvent solubility parameter on the dispersion of clay. Liu *et al.*¹⁴ have done a similar work with carbon nanotubes. Hansen solubility (cohesion) parameters (HSP) are extensively used for the prediction of the compati-

lity between two materials. Materials with similar HSP will exhibit physical affinities for each other. Barton has also given a detailed description on the application of HSP¹⁵. Chlorobutyl rubber, a special class of butyl rubber that is chlorinated has been chosen for this study. As a result of its molecular structure, the elastomer possesses superior air impermeability due to the sluggish movement of its methyl groups. The outstanding air impermeability of chlorobutyl rubber has made it the material suitable for the inner tubes and liners of tires. In addition to this application which consumes a vital part of its annual production, chlorobutyl rubber is also used in mechanical damping applications due to its high loss modulus, extended fatigue life and oxidative stability. The purpose of this work was, therefore, to investigate the relationship between the degree of exfoliation of organoclays and properties of the solvent in which the clays were dispersed by utilizing the corresponding solvent solubility parameters. Also the paper tries to establish that the nature of organic modification, d-spacing etc. of the layered silicate play a vital role in tailoring the properties of the composite.

Results and discussion

Analysis of the XRD patterns (Fig. 1) clearly reveal that the polymer chains are intercalated within the gallery spaces of the layered silicates. The pristine clay is show-

Fig. 1. XRD plot of chlorobutyl rubber nanocomposites with cloisite 15A (5 phr) in different solvents.

ing a peak at $2\theta = 2.75$. The nanocomposite prepared using chloroform as the solvent shows two small peaks. One at a lower ($2\theta = 2.2$) value than that shown by the layered silicate and the second peak is close to the peak shown by the pristine clay. This suggests that chloroform was not so effective in dispersing the clay platelets and the occurrence of the second peak shows that some of the clay layers remained as tactoids in the rubber matrix. Similar is the observation shown by THF but the shift in the first peak in this case is towards a lower 2θ value (i.e. $2\theta = 2$) than that shown by chloroform suggesting better dispersion. In the case of toluene, xylene and cyclohexane the peaks remain at a slightly lower 2θ value than that of pristine clay ($2\theta = 2$) indicating intercalation of polymer chains and there is no occurrence second peak near the peak for the pristine clay. This is clear from the TEM shown in Fig. 2. Similarly TEM of nanocomposites containing 5 phr of different moieties of layered silicates is shown in Fig. 3 which shows effective dispersion of cloisite 15A in the CIIR matrix.

Fig. 2. TEM micrographs of nanocomposites containing (a) 5 phr of cloisite 15A and (b) 5 phr of cloisite 10A.

Fig. 3. TEM micrographs of nanocomposites containing 5 phr of cloisite 15A in (a) chloroform, (b) THF and (c) cyclohexane.

Experimental

The nanocomposites were prepared by a novel method in which solution mixing was followed by the addition of compounding ingredients on a two roll mill. Mixing on two roll mill was carried out for a period of 15 min by carefully controlling the nip gap and temperature. The preparation of the nanocomposites was carried out using a range of solvents like cyclohexane, toluene, xylene, tetrahydrofuran, chloroform etc. The compounds were mixed in a two-roll mill of 170 mm diameter, working distance 300 mm, speed of slow roll 18 rpm, and gear ratio 1 : 4 by careful control of temperature, nip gap, and time of mixing using a sulphur cure package. The CIIR composites were left for a day before vulcanization in the normal air.

Conclusion

Chlorobutyl rubber nanocomposites were prepared using different solvents with varying like cyclohexane, chloroform, toluene, xylene and tetrahydrofuran. The variation in the properties of the nanocomposites clearly indicates that the choice of the proper solvent is highly essential for the successful fabrication of a composites material by solution mixing process. It can be assumed that decoiling of the CIIR chains in toluene, xylene and cyclohexane as a result of similar polarity and solubility parameter values leads to complete exfoliation of the organoclay, thereby providing excellent mechanical properties. Moreover it is clear from the exfoliated/intercalated geometry of the nanocomposites that they will surely exhibit novel gas barrier properties which enable them to be used as barrier materials. The enhancement in properties showed by layered silicate moieties with different modifications can be explained on the basis of the type of modification and d-spacing. This in turn helps in the tai-

ling of the properties of the layered silicate nanocomposites for a variety of advanced applications.

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